

Six new species of *Nososticta* Hagen, 1860 from Papua New Guinea (Odonata: Platycnemididae)

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Abstract. The males and, when available, females of six new species of the damselfly genus *Nososticta* are described from the upper Fly, Strickland, and Kikori River basins in southern Papua New Guinea. They are *Nososticta caelestis* sp. nov. (♂ holotype, 10-viii-2014), *Nososticta chrismulleri* sp. nov. (♂ holotype, 04-viii-2013), *Nososticta makrodon* sp. nov. (♂ holotype, 01-viii-2013), *Nososticta megantereon* sp. nov. (♂ holotype, 03-viii-2013, ♀ described), *Nososticta ovimacula* sp. nov. (♂ holotype, 29-vii-2013, ♀ described), and *Nososticta paracanifera* sp. nov. (♂ holotype, 02-viii-2013, ♀ described).

Further key words. Dragonfly, damselfly, Zygoptera

Introduction

Damselflies of the platycnemidid genus *Nososticta* are a conspicuous element of the New Guinea odonate fauna, occurring at small brooks and larger rivers throughout the lowlands and foothills. The genus is diverse and many species are brightly coloured, but the group remains poorly documented with THEISCHINGER & RICHARDS (2015a) recently increasing the number of *Nososticta* species known from the Papuan region by almost 25% to 47. That paper predicted the discovery of several more dozens of species in the region, and two more species were subsequently described in the same year (THEISCHINGER et al. 2015; THEISCHINGER & RICHARDS 2015b). Here we describe and illustrate a further six new species from southern Papua New Guinea, and provide images of three poorly-known sympatric congeners.

Material and methods

Descriptive terminology largely follows WATSON & O'FARRELL (1991). Col-oration is given as detectable from the preserved material, supplemented with photographs of specimens taken in life. Measurements are given in millimeters (mm). All illustrations were done with the aid of a camera lu-cida and are not to scale. Coordinates are presented using the GPS datum WGS 84. Material is lodged in the collection of the South Australian Mu-seum in Adelaide, Australia (SAMA), and representative samples will be deposited in Papua New Guinea if a suitable repository becomes available there. To facilitate comparisons among species, descriptions are presented according to the species-groups that were defined by THEISCHINGER & RI-CHARDS (2015a). These groups are recognised in order to facilitate identifi-cation and probably do not represent monophyletic groups.

Group A: Males with front of synthorax completely black, without any pale ante-humeral patches

Nososticta megantereon sp. nov.

(Photo 1, Figs 1–6)

Material studied

Holotype ♂. (SAMA 07-001431), Papua New Guinea, Western Province, upper Strickland River basin, Camp 5 (6°16.581'S, 142°06.132'E; 110 m a.s.l.), 05-viii-2013, S.J. Richards leg.

Paratypes (all from Papua New Guinea). 1♂ (SAMA 07-001432), same data as holotype; 1♀ (SAMA 07-001433), type locality, 06-viii-2013; 1♂ (SAMA 07-001434), 02-viii-2014; 1♂, 1♀ (copula) (SAMA 07-001435–36), 03-viii-2014, Southern Highlands Province, upper Kikori River basin, Camp 7 (6°26.900'S, 142°57.587'E; 365 m a.s.l.); 1♂ (SAMA 07-001437), 11-viii-2014, 1♂ (SAMA 07-001438), 14-viii-2014, Western Province, upper Strickland River basin, Camp 6 (6°26.132'S, 142°33.695'E; 380 m a.s.l.); all S.J. Richards leg.

Etymology

Megantereon, here used as a noun in apposition, is the generic name of a fos-sil creature close to *Smilodon* (saber-toothed cat). This name reflects the ap-

Photos 1–3. *Nososticta* spp., males in life, southern Papua New Guinea: 1 – *N. megantereon* sp. nov., Photo: SJR (05-viii-2013); 2 – *N. makrodon* sp. nov., Photo: SJR (09-viii-2014); 3 – *N. caelestis* sp. nov., Photo: SJR (10-viii-2014)

parent close affinity of the new species to *Nososticta smilodon* Theischinger & Richards, 2006.

A black species with pale (bluish/whitish/yellowish) pattern well developed on head and thorax, poorly developed on abdomen, the wings hyaline. No ante-humeral mark and a tiny remnant of a pale mesepimeral patch combined with an almost full-length metanepisternal patch; metepimeral patch substantial. Abdomen, except for intersegmental membranes of S8 and S9, dorsally black. Superior anal appendages of male bright orange to brownish yellow and very long.

Male (holotype)

Head – Largely black; only basal $\frac{2}{3}$ of labium pale yellow and a narrow transverse frontal bar from eye to eye pale blue.

Thorax – Prothorax: Notum and most of episternum black, ventral portion of episternum and epimeron pale yellowish green. Synthorax (Fig. 1): Pleura largely black; pale (bluish/whitish/yellowish) metepisternal and metepimeral stripe, separated by ill-defined dark patch along metapleural suture, a tiny stripe of mesepimeron, tip of katepisterna and postcoxae yellowish white to pale brownish yellow. Poststernum yellowish to greyish white.

Legs: Coxae yellow to greyish brown; trochanters and base of femora brownish yellow, this least extensive on profemur, more extensive on mesofemur and most extensive on metafemur; remainder of legs largely black, outer face of meso- and metatibia greyish brown.

Wings – Membrane hyaline, venation black; pterostigma approximately 1.8 times as long as wide, black, with very narrow hyaline margin, particularly along posterior and distal border; postnodals 18/15–17; no transverse cross-vein descending from distal margin of discoidal cell to wing margin.

Abdomen – S1 dorsally black, laterally almost entirely pale brownish yellow; S2 black, with large brownish yellow patch adjacent to genitalia; S3–8 black, merging into brown ventrally; S9 and S10 black, only intersegmental membrane between S8 and S9 and between S9 and S10 yellow.

Anal appendages (Figs 2, 3): Bright orange to brownish yellow, superiors drawn out into long, pointed dorsal cone, inferiors with strongly developed base.

Measurements [mm] – Hind wing 18.7; abdomen (including anal appendages) 33.9.

Female

Head – Very similar to male, but base of prementum whitish yellow and pale greyish brown and transverse frontal bar pale brownish yellow.

Thorax – Prothorax (Figs 4, 5): Notum and most of pleura black, only postero-ventral tip of episternum and ventral portion of epimeron yellowish white. Posterior lobe of notum rather upright, tri-lobed with short wide median lobe and each side a large rounded lateral lobe that is proximally drawn out into a finger-like process; a small knob-like elevation between median and lateral lobes. Synthorax (Fig. 6): Much as in male but area along metapleural suture between dull white stripes smaller and better defined, and postcoxae and poststernum dull white.

Legs with coxae and trochanters dull white to pale yellow, remainder of legs largely black with only extreme base of pro- and mesofemur and basal $\frac{2}{3}$ of metafemur whitish yellow to greyish yellow and outer face of meso- and metatibia yellowish grey.

Wings – Much as in male but pterostigma slightly paler, almost twice as long as wide and with hyaline margins less strongly apparent; postnodals 16–17/14.

Abdomen – S1 dorsally black, laterally pale yellowish white; S2–10 largely black, latero-ventrally merging into greyish brown to greyish white in S2–7, S3 in addition with yellowish white basal spot, S8 and S9 with well-defined yellowish white stripe along ventral margin. Anal appendages black. Valves largely black, reaching backward beyond the end of S10 by approximately length of S10 and with approximately 15 sharp teeth along ventral edge; terebra dark reddish brown.

Measurements [mm] – Hind wing 20.2; abdomen 31.4.

Variability

The paratype males agree very well with the holotype in coloration. Post-nodals 17–21/15–17. Measurements [mm]: Hind wing 18.9–21.6, abdomen (including anal appendages) 34.1–40.5.

Habitat

This species was most commonly encountered in sun patches adjacent to small (<5 m wide) clear, flowing streams in lowland rainforest where they perched on low foliage less than 50 cm high. It is currently known only from the upper Strickland and Kikori River basins in southern Papua New Guinea.

Differential diagnosis

Because the front of the male synthorax is completely black, without any pale ante-humeral marking, *N. megantereon* sp. nov. belongs in Group A of THEISCHINGER & RICHARDS (2015a). Within Group A it differs from all species except *N. acuminata* Michalski, Richards & Theischinger, 2012, *N. atrocyana* (Lieftinck, 1960), *N. longicauda* Theischinger & Richards, 2015, and *N. smilodon* in having the frontal fascia blue (*vs* white, yellow, orange or entirely absent). It can be distinguished from *N. acuminata* by having S8–10 all black (*vs* 9–10 marked dorsally with orange/yellow) and the superior anal appendages drawn out into a long, pointed dorsal cone (*vs* superior anal appendages with tip thinly attenuated); it can be distinguished from *N. atrocyana* by the shape of the superior appendages, which are not drawn out into a dorsal cone in that species (see Fig. 1 in THEISCHINGER & RICHARDS 2015a); it is distinguished from *N. longicauda* in having S10 black (*vs* marked dorsally with orange/yellow) and by the shape of the superior appendages (long, shallow, and almost parallel-sided with blunt tips in *longicauda*). The new species is most similar to, and probably most closely related to, *N. smilodon*. The male of *N. megantereon* can be distinguished from *N. smilodon* by S8–10 being all black (*vs* at least S10 dorsally yellow in *N. smilodon*) and by the greatly elongated apex of the superior anal appendages.

Figures 1–12. *Nososticta* spp.: 1–6) *Nososticta megantereon* sp. nov.: 1–3) male: 1) synthorax, frontal, lateral, ventral; 2, 3) anal appendages, dorsal and lateral; 4–6) female: 4) posterior lobe of pronotum, dorsal; 5) pronotum, lateral; 6) synthorax, frontal, lateral, ventral. 7–9) *Nososticta makrodon* sp. nov, male: 7) synthorax, frontal, lateral, ventral; 8, 9) anal appendages, frontal and lateral. 10–12) *Nososticta caelestis* sp. nov.: 10) synthorax, frontal, lateral, ventral; 11, 12) anal appendages, dorsal and lateral.

Group B: Front of male synthorax with patches of orange

Nososticta makrodon sp. nov.

(Photo 2, Figs 7–9)

Material studied

Holotype ♂. (SAMA 07-001439), Papua New Guinea, Western Province, Palmer River Catchment, upper Fly River basin, Camp 4 (5°54.477'S, 141°50.773'E; 125 m a.s.l.), 01-viii-2013, S.J. Richards leg.

Paratypes (all from Papua New Guinea), Western Province, upper Strickland River basin, Camp 5, (6°16.581'S, 142°06.132'E; 110 m a.s.l.). 1♂ (SAMA 07-001440), 05-viii-2013, 2♂ (SAMA 07-001441–42), 11-viii-2013; all S.J. Richards leg.

Etymology

The specific name, a noun in apposition, is a composite of μακρός [makros] (= Greek for large) and ὀδών [odon] (= Greek for tooth) refers to the large tooth on the superior anal appendages of the male.

A black species, the male with large orange ante-humeral patch, otherwise with pale (whitish/yellowish/bluish) pattern on head and thorax well developed and rather poorly developed on the abdomen. Pale mesepimeral patch almost completely undeveloped. Wings with greenish brown tinge. Superior anal appendages of the male bright/pale (whitish/yellowish), simple but with very large ventral tooth.

Male (holotype)

Head – Largely black; only most of labium pale greyish to brownish yellow and a transverse frontal bar from eye to eye whitish yellow.

Thorax – Prothorax: Notum black; pleura whitish yellow, black along suture. Synthorax (Fig. 7): Pleura largely black; ante-humeral patch orange, approximately $\frac{3}{5}$ the length of mesanepisternum, basally about twice as wide as dorsally, middorsal area of separation trapezoidal; posterior corner of mesokatepisternum, much of metanepisternum, posterior corner of metakatepisternum and most of metepimeron pale yellow. Postcoxae and poststernum yellowish white.

Legs: Coxae, trochanters, and basal portion of femora whitish yellow, remainder greyish brown to black with outer face of meso- and metatibia palest.

Wings – Membrane with slight greenish brown tinge, venation black; pterostigma black with narrow pale margin, almost twice as long as wide; postnodals 15/13; a transverse cross-vein descending from distal margin of discoidal cell to wing margin.

Abdomen – S1 dorsally blackish brown, laterally pale yellow; S2–8 dorsally largely brownish black (S2 dorsally with slight indication of ill-defined, irregular-sized and shaped, paler cloud), merging into brown and paler laterally/ventrally; a small whitish yellow lateral spot at the base of S3; S9 and S10 black.

Anal appendages (Figs 8, 9): Superiors whitish yellow, short, with large ventral tooth, inferiors greyish brown to black.

Measurements [mm] – Hind wing 17.6; abdomen (including anal appendages) 29.0.

Female

Unknown.

Variability

The paratype males agree well with the holotype in coloration and pattern. Postnodals 15–16/13–14. Measurements [mm]: Hind wing 17.0–18.0; abdomen (including anal appendages) 28.3–31.0.

Habitat

This species was common along small to large (~1–5 m wide), clear streams flowing over sandy, muddy, and rocky substrates in lowland rainforest. Males perched on low vegetation in sun patches adjacent to the streams, and also on small twigs and branches over the water surface. It is currently known only from the upper Fly and Strickland River basins in southern Papua New Guinea.

Differential diagnosis

Nososticta makrodon sp. nov. fits into Group B (male synthorax with patches of orange) of THEISCHINGER & RICHARDS (2015a). It can be distinguished from all members of the group except *N. rangifera* (Liefstinck, 1949), *N. rosea rosea* (Ris, 1913), *N. r. cruentata* (Liefstinck, 1932) and *N. xanthe* (Liefstinck, 1938), by having the pale/bright ante-humeral patch or pale ante-humeral plus mesepimeral patch isolated from the pale metepisternal patch (*vs* pale/bright ante-humeral patch, pale mesepimeral patch and pale metepisternal patch broadly connected or adjacent). It can be distinguished from *N. rosea rosea* and *N. r. cruentata* by having the superior anal appendages very pale, short, and with large ventral tooth (*vs* much darker, longer, and with small ventral tooth). It can be distinguished from *N. xanthe* by having the orange ante-humeral patches markedly shorter than the mesepisternum (*vs* almost as long as mesepisternum). It is most similar to, and probably the closest ally of, *N. rangifera* from which it can be distinguished by having a distinctly trapezoidal area medially separating the basally wide, dorsally narrow orange ante-humeral patches (*vs* area of separation and patches approximately parallel sided in *N. rangifera*).

Group C. Males with front of synthorax with patches of blue, yellow or green; tip of abdomen blue

Nososticta caelestis sp. nov.

(Photo 3, Fig. 10–12)

Material studied

Holotype ♂. (SAMA 07-001443), Papua New Guinea, Western Province, upper Strickland River basin, Camp 6, (6°26.132'S, 142°33.695'E; 380 m a.s.l.), 10-viii-2014, S.J. Richards leg.

Paratype. 1 ♂ (SAMA 07-001444), same locality as holotype, 11-viii-2014, S.J. Richards leg.

Etymology

The specific name *caelestis*, *-e* is a Latin adjective meaning 'heavenly' and refers to the sky blue markings of the species.

A black species, the male with bright blue pattern on head and thorax; wings slightly suffused with greenish yellow, abdomen largely black with superi-

or anal appendages blue. Blue ante-humeral patch some distance from the mesokatepisternum and similar in size to mesepimeral patch.

Male (holotype)

Head – Largely black; only base of labium whitish to yellowish grey and a rather wide bar from eye to eye across anterior frons and genae adjacent to postclypeus sky blue.

Thorax – Prothorax almost completely black, only a sky blue spot on epimeron; median lobe of notum bi-conical and rugose. Synthoracic pleura (Fig. 10) largely black with pale patches as follows (Photo 3, Fig. 10): mesepisternal, mesepimeral, and metepisternal patches bright azure; metepimeral patch markedly paler blue. Poststernum and postcoxae brown.

Legs largely black, only metacoxa, metatrochanter, and metafemur somewhat paler.

Wings – Venation black; membrane slightly suffused with greenish yellow; pterostigma slightly widening distally, at least twice as long as wide, overlying slightly less to slightly more than $1\frac{1}{2}$ cells; 14–15/13 postnodals; a transverse cross-vein descending from distal margin of discoidal cell to wing margin; CuP reaching wing margin between $\frac{1}{3}$ and $\frac{1}{2}$ length of first cell following discoidal cell.

Abdomen – Largely black; S1 and S2 with pale lateral patch, pale blue in S1, pale bluish grey in S2; S3–S9 with ventral margin narrowly pale. Anal appendages (Figs 11, 12): Superiors pale blue with rather slim pointed tooth, inferiors brownish grey with base wide-angled.

Measurements [mm] – Hind wing 19.5; abdomen (incl. appendages) 31.0.

Female

Unknown.

Habitat

The two known specimens were collected from twigs hanging just above the water surface over small (<5 m wide) shallow sandy streams in hill forest.

This species is known only from the upper Strickland River basin in southern Papua New Guinea.

Variability

The paratype agrees well with the holotype; it appears slightly less mature and is slightly paler, has 15/13 postnodals, a hind wing length of 20.0 and an abdomen plus appendages length of 31.3 mm.

Differential diagnosis

N. caelestis sp. nov. fits into Group C (species with front of male synthorax with patches of blue, yellow or green and with tip of male abdomen blue) of THEISCHINGER & RICHARDS (2015a). It can be distinguished from all members of this group except *N. azurosignata* Theischinger & Richards, 2015 and *N. truncata* Theischinger & Richards, 2015 by having ante-humeral and mesepimeral patches of subequal size and metepisternal patch not reaching the ventral border of metepisternum. *N. caelestis* differs from *N. azurosignata* and *N. truncata* by having the ante-humeral patch some distance from the mesokatepisternum and a rather slim ventral tooth on the superior anal appendages and a wide-angled base of the inferiors (*vs* ante-humeral patch adjacent to mesokatepisternum in both *N. azurosignata* and *N. truncata*, and a large ventral tooth on the superior anal appendages and a rather right-angled base of the inferiors in *N. azurosignata* and rather parallel sided, truncate superior anal appendages without any sign of a ventral tooth in *N. truncata*). The anal appendages of *N. caelestis* are very similar to those of *N. conifera* Theischinger & Richards, 2006 and *N. paraconifera* sp. nov., but these two species have a much larger blue mesepimeral patch, and *N. paraconifera* in addition lacks a blue frontal bar.

Nososticta paraconifera sp. nov.

(Photo 4, Figs 13–19)

Material studied

Holotype ♂. (SAMA 07-001445), Papua New Guinea, Western Province, Palmer River Catchment, upper Fly River basin, Camp 4 (5°54.477'S, 141°50.773'E; 125 m a.s.l.), 02-viii-2013, S.J. Richards leg.

Paratypes (all from type locality). 1♂, 1♀ (SAMA 07-001446–47), 02-viii-2013; 1♂ (SAMA 07-001448), 28-vii-2013; all S.J. Richards leg.

Etymology

The specific name, a declinable adjective, refers to the morphological similarity of *N. paraconifera* sp. nov. to *N. conifera* Theischinger & Richards, 2006.

A basically black species, the male with the blue/pale pattern reduced to front and sides of the synthorax and to the superior anal appendages, the wings hyaline. Male with ante-humeral patch very small and mesepimeral and metepisternal patch not reaching across the whole length of these pleura. Female with very distinct orange frontal bar, mesanepisternum and mesepimeron almost completely black and abdomen dorsally black but with light anal appendages.

Male (holotype)

Head – Largely black; only base of labium whitish to brownish yellow and tips of mandibles reddish to blackish brown.

Thorax – Prothorax (Fig. 13): Black; median lobe of notum raised into a somewhat rugose cone on each side. Synthorax (Fig. 17): Pleura largely black; ante-humeral patch dark blue, less than $\frac{1}{3}$ as long and approximately $\frac{1}{3}$ as wide as mesanepisternum, connected to blue patch that extends across $\frac{2}{3}$ length of mesepimeron and is again connected to a paler blue patch which covers approximately anterior $\frac{2}{3}$ width across approximately $\frac{3}{4}$ length of metepisternum and is widely separated from narrow, pale blue subtriangular metepimeral patch. Poststernum pale greyish yellow with ill-defined brownish-black anterior lateral patch and larger basal brownish black medial patch.

Legs: Largely black, only coxae and extreme bases of femora slightly paler.

Wings – Membrane hyaline, venation black; pterostigma black, slightly more than twice as long as wide; postnodals 15/14; a transverse cross-vein descending from distal margin of discoidal cell to wing margin.

Photos 4–5. *Nososticta* spp., males in life, southern Papua New Guinea: 4 – *N. paraconifera* sp. nov. Photo: SJR (28-vii-2013); 5 – *N. chrismulleri* sp. nov. Photo: SJR (29-vii-2013)

Abdomen – S1 dorsally black, laterally black with blue postero-ventral patch; S2 black, pale yellow adjacent to genitalia; S3–7 black, ventrally narrowly margined greyish yellow; S8, S9, and S10 black.

Anal appendages (Figs 15, 16): Superiors blue, inferiors greyish yellow to greyish brown.

Measurements [mm] – Hind wing 18.8; abdomen (including anal appendages) 30.6.

Female

Head – Much as in male but with very conspicuous broad somewhat sinuous dark yellow to pale orange frontal bar (from eye to eye) that also covers part of the antennal base.

Figures 13–19. *Nososticta paraconifera* sp. nov.: 13–16) male: 13) pronotum, lateral; 14) synthorax, frontal, lateral, ventral; 15, 16) anal appendages, dorsal and lateral; 17–19) female: 17) posterior lobe of pronotum, dorsal; 18) pronotum, lateral; 19) synthorax, frontal, lateral, ventral.

Thorax – Prothorax (Figs 17, 18): Much as in male but notum brown to black and epimeron greyish black. Median lobe of notum with median lobe distinctly bi-conical and posterior lobe as seen in dorsal view with fish-tail-like median lobe and each side with two lateral structures, the outer a wide lobe with finger-like appendix directed somewhat backward, the inner much smaller and rounded to subtriangular. Synthorax (Fig. 19): Most of mesepisternum and mesepimeron black but on anepisternum latero-basally slightly less dark; other dark areas somewhat paler and blue areas less bright than in male; area ventral to metathoracic spiracle dark dull yellow.

Legs much as in male but coxae and trochanters pale greyish brown and pale at base of femora, particularly metafemur, more extensive and at least outer face of meso- and metatibia greyish brown.

Wings much as in male; postnodals 13–14/12–13.

Abdomen – Dorsally black. Side of S1 largely brown; S2–7 pale along latero-ventral edge, this decreasing in width from S2 to S7, slightly wider again and better defined in S8 and S9. Anal appendages dull yellowish white. Valves black, reaching backward beyond end of S10 by about three times the length of S10, approximately 15 sharply pointed teeth along ventral margin; terebra brown to black.

Measurements [mm] – Hind wing 19.2; abdomen 29.3.

Variability

The paratype males agree well with the holotype in coloration. Antenodals 15–16/12–14. Measurements [mm]: Hind wing 18.2–19.1; abdomen (including anal appendages) 28.3–31.3.

Habitat

This species was uncommon, and occurred patchily along small (<5 m wide), clear streams flowing over rocky and sandy substrates in lowland rainforest. Males and females were normally perched within 1 m of the stream, on small twigs and leaves in sun patches in otherwise heavily shaded forest with extensive canopy cover. It is currently known only from the upper Fly River basin in southern Papua New Guinea.

Differential diagnosis

Nososticta paraconifera sp. nov. fits into group C (species with front of male synthorax with patches of blue, yellow or green and with tip of male abdomen blue) of THEISCHINGER & RICHARDS (2015a). It differs from all members of the group except *N. conifera* Theischinger & Richards, 2006 and *N. nigrifrons* (Ris, 1913) in having the ante-humeral patch greatly reduced in size (compared with mesepimeral patch) and the metepisternal patch not reaching the ventral border of the metepisternum (*vs* ante-humeral patch not greatly reduced in size and metepisternal patch reaching the ventral border of the metepisternum). The male of *N. paraconifera* sp. nov. can be distinguished from *N. conifera* by lacking a blue frontal bar between the eyes and from *N. nigrifrons* by having superior anal appendages with simple slim apex (*vs* with truncate, ventrally expanded apex in *N. nigrifrons*).

***Nososticta chrismulleri* sp. nov.**

(Photo 5, Figs 20–23)

Material studied

Holotype ♂. (SAMA 07-001449), Papua New Guinea, Western Province, Palmer River Catchment, upper Fly River basin, Camp 4 (5°54.477'S, 141°50.773'E; 125 m a.s.l.), 02-viii-2013, S.J. Richards leg.

Etymology

The species is dedicated to Chris Muller who collected a number of interesting odonates for the second author, and provided much appreciated camaraderie in remote bush camps throughout Papua New Guinea. In appreciation of adventures shared.

A black species, the male with blue pattern on head, thorax, and abdomen, the wings with greenish brown tinge. Ante-humeral patch slightly longer than $\frac{1}{2}$ of mesanepisternum, the mesepimeral patch without any anterior step and about $\frac{3}{4}$ as long as pleuron in male, reduced to a narrow stripe in female. Much of S8 blue.

Male (holotype)

Head – Largely black; only base of labium pale grey and a transverse frontal bar from eye to eye bright blue.

Thorax – Prothorax: Notum black with blue lateral spot on anterior lobe connected to large blue lateral patch on median lobe, pleura largely bright blue, black along suture and at rear of epimeron. Synthorax (Fig. 20): Pleura largely black; ante-humeral patch bright blue, slightly longer than $\frac{1}{2}$ the length of mesanepisternum, basally approximately twice as wide as dorsally; also blue a patch without anterior step and covering about $\frac{3}{4}$ length of mesepimeron, and partly connected with a stripe across the whole length and the anterior $\frac{2}{3}$ of metepisternum, and a blue patch across the postero-dorsal half of metepimeron. Postcoxae largely blackish brown to black; poststernum bluish white with ill-defined patches of blackish brown to black.

Legs: Coxae and trochanters black and blue, legs otherwise black, with only basal inner portion of metafemur pale blue to pale and brownish yellow.

Wings – Membrane with greenish brown tinge, venation black; pterostigma black, approximately twice as long as wide; postnodals 16–17/14; a transverse cross-vein descending from distal margin of discoidal cell to wing margin.

Abdomen – S1 dorsally black, laterally largely pale blue; S2 black, pale blue adjacent to genitalia; S3–7 dorsally black, ventrally margined greyish brown to dull yellow, S3–S6 with blue mid-dorsal spot very close to base; S8 largely blue, narrowly lined black basally, more widely and irregularly apically; S9 and S10 black.

Anal appendages (Figs 21–23): Superiors largely blue with large tooth some distance from apex and therefore mostly visible only from caudal aspect, inferiors brownish black.

Measurements [mm] – Hind wing 19.1; abdomen (including anal appendages) 33.0.

Female

Unknown.

Habitat

This species was found along small to large (ca 1–5 m wide), clear streams flowing over sandy and rocky substrates in lowland rainforest. Males perched on low vegetation in sun patches adjacent to the streams, and also

Figures 20–29. *Nososticta* spp.: 20–23) *Nososticta chrismulleri* sp. nov., male: 20) synthorax, frontal, lateral, ventral; 21, 22) anal appendages, dorsal and lateral; 23) superior anal appendages, caudal. 24–29) *Nososticta ovimacula* sp. nov.: 24–26) male: 24) synthorax, frontal, lateral, ventral; 25, 26) anal appendages, dorsal and lateral; 27–29) female: 27) synthorax, frontal, lateral, ventral; 28) posterior lobe of pronotum, dorsal; 29) pronotum, lateral.

on small twigs and branches over the water surface. It is currently known only from the upper Fly River basin in southern Papua New Guinea.

Differential diagnosis

Nososticta chrismulleri sp. nov. fits into group C (species with front of male synthorax with patches of blue, yellow or green and with tip of male abdomen blue) of THEISCHINGER & RICHARDS (2015a). It is similar in thoracic pattern to *N. salomonis* (Selys, 1886), *N. africana* (Schmidt, 1944) and *N. commutata* (Lieftinck, 1938). The blue ante-humeral patch of the male is considerably longer than in *N. salomonis* and *N. commutata*, and there is no blue dorsal marking on S2 as opposed to its presence in *N. africana*. The new species appears closest to *N. salomonis* but the male can be distinguished from this species by the spotted anterior lobe of the pronotum, the markedly longer blue ante-humeral patch, and the lack of a step in the blue mesepimeral patch.

Group D. Males with front of synthorax with patches of blue, yellow or green; tip of abdomen not blue

Nososticta ovimacula sp. nov.

(Photos 6, 7, Figs 24–29)

Material studied

Holotype ♂. (SAMA 07-001450), Papua New Guinea, Western Province, Palmer River Catchment, upper Fly River basin, Camp 4 (5°54.477'S, 141°50.773'E; 125 m a.s.l.), 29-vii-2013, S.J. Richards leg.

Paratypes. 1♂, 1♀ (SAMA 07-001333-34), same data as holotype; 1♀ (SAMA 07-001335), Papua New Guinea, Southern Highlands Province, upper Kikori River basin, Camp 7 (6°26.900'S, 142°57.587'E; 365 m a.s.l.), 01-viii-2014, all S.J. Richards leg.

Etymology

The specific name *ovimacula*, a noun, is composed of *ovi* = genitive case of *ovum*, *-i* (Latin for egg) and *macula* = ablative case of *macula*, *-ae* (Latin for spot), refers to the large egg-shaped patch on the mesanepisternum of the male and translates 'with egg-spot'.

Photos 6–9. *Nososticta* spp. in life, southern Papua New Guinea: 6 – *N. ovimacula* sp. nov., male. Photo SJR (29-vii-2013); 7 – *N. ovimacula* sp. nov., female. Photo: SJR (29-vii-2013); 8 – *N. marina*, male. Photo: SJR (09-viii-2013); 9 – *N. rosea*, male. Photo: SJR (28-vii-2013)

A black species with blue pattern on head and thorax and poorly developed on abdomen; anal appendages black; wings hyaline. Male with very large oval ante-humeral patch and separate metepisternal and metepimeral patch, both across the entire length of the respective pleuron. Female with ante-humeral patch much smaller and metepisternal patch shorter than in male.

Male (holotype)

Head – Largely shining black; only base of labium whitish yellow and a transverse frontal bar from eye to eye bluish white.

Thorax – Prothorax: Notum black; pleura bluish white, narrowly black along suture. Synthorax (Fig. 24): Pleura largely shining black; ante-humeral patch pale blue, at least $\frac{1}{2}$ as long and $\frac{1}{2}$ as wide as mesanepisternum; a bluish white yellow patch across approximately $\frac{2}{3}$ width and whole length of mesepimeron and an almost white patch covering approximately posterior $\frac{2}{3}$ and the whole length of metepimeron. Poststernum yellowish white.

Legs: Largely greyish brown to black; most of procoxa, posterior portion of meso- and metacoxa, and trochanters and base of metafemur pale to greyish yellow.

Wings – Membrane hyaline, venation black; pterostigma grey with narrow pale margin, slightly less than twice as long as wide; postnodals 17–18/15; no transverse cross-vein descending from distal margin of discoidal cell to wing margin.

Abdomen – S1 dorsally shining black, laterally yellowish to bluish white with black spot; S2–8 shining black, ventrally narrowly margined with pale greyish brown; an indication of a whitish basal lateral spot in S3; S9 and S10 black.

Anal appendages (Figs 25, 26): Superiors largely black, not much longer than S10, inferiors also largely black, with base not prominent.

Measurements [mm] – Hind wing 19.2; abdomen (including anal appendages) 31.7.

Female

Head – Much as in male but slightly paler.

Thorax – Prothorax (Figs 28, 29): Coloration much as in male. Median lobe of notum rounded; posterior lobe with slightly bi-lobed wide median lobe bearing on each side a strong bifid structure with anterior branch long, finger-like and pointing dorsad, posterior branch robust, subtriangular and directed slightly backward; a small backward directed lobe protrudes from under this structure. Synthorax (Fig. 27): Coloration much as in male but pale areas generally even paler; ante-humeral patch less than half as long and approximately half as wide as mesanepisternum; pale metathoracic areas slightly smaller than in male; poststernum slightly clouded with darker.

Legs much as in male but slightly paler.

Wings – Much as in male; postnodals 17/15; a transverse cross-vein descending from distal margin of discoidal cell to wing margin in both hind wings.

Abdomen – Much as in male but slightly paler; pale ventral edge of S8 wider and more distinct; S9 ventrally also edged pale. Anal appendages black. Valves reaching backward beyond end of S10 by about the length of S10; approximately 10 sharp teeth detectable along ventral edge; terebra brown.

Measurements [mm] – Hind wing 18.4; abdomen 29.7.

Variability

The paratype male agrees with the holotype in coloration and pattern. Postnodals 18–20/17. Measurements [mm]: Hind wing 19.0; abdomen (including anal appendages) 31.2.

Habitat

This species was less closely associated with streams than other *Nososticta* encountered in the upper Strickland River basin. All four types were perched *ca* 1–2 m high on vegetation in sunny patches in lowland rainforest at least 10 m from the nearest flowing streams. *Nososticta ovimacula* sp. nov. is cur-

rently known only from the upper Fly and Kikori River basins in southern Papua New Guinea.

Differential diagnosis

N. ovimacula sp. nov. belongs in Group D (species with front of male synthorax with patches of blue, yellow or green and with tip of male abdomen not blue) of THEISCHINGER & RICHARDS (2015a) The extremely large, blue, oval ante-humeral spot, covering almost all of the male mesanepisternum appears to be unique among Papuan *Nososticta* and immediately distinguishes *N. ovimacula* sp. nov. from all congeners in this group. The species bears some resemblance to *N. interrupta* Theischinger & Richards, 2015, but the male of that species has the blue frontal bar medially interrupted and a much smaller ante-humeral patch.

Additional species

A number of additional *Nososticta* species were encountered in the upper Fly, Strickland, and Kikori River basins, and eight members of the genus occurred syntopically at Camp 4. Three of these are the poorly-known *Nososticta marina* (Ris, 1913) (Photo 8), *N. rosea* (Ris, 1913) (Photo 9) and *N. truncata* Theischinger & Richards, 2015 (Photo 10). They are illustrated

Photo 10. *Nososticta truncata*, male in life, upper Fly River basin, Papua New Guinea. Photo: SJR (01-viii-2013)

here for the first time to provide information on their colours and general body form in life.

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Photo 11. Typical stream habitat for *Nososticta* species in the upper Strickland River basin, Papua New Guinea. Eight species of the genus occurred within a 250 m radius of this site. Photo: SJR (01-viii-2013)

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